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Implementation of Government Regulation No. 53/2010 About Civil State Employees Discipline In General and Equipment of Regional Secretariat Halmahera

Abdulhalil Hi. Ibrahim

Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia
Corresponding author email: chalilibrahim101@gmail.com

Syofyan Saraha

Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia
Email: saraha@gmail.com

Abdurahman Kader

Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia
Email: kaderummu@gmail.com

Mikael Iriyanto

Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia
Email: mikaelummu@gmail.com

Rasid Pora

Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia
Email: porarasyid@gmail.com

Abstract---This study aimed to determine the implementation of Government Regulation no. 53 of 2010 on the Civil Servant Discipline I Division of General and Secretariat Supplies Daerah Kabupaten West Halmahera. The results show that the implementation of Government Regulation No. 53/2010 in the general and equipment section has been running quite well, but some violate these rules. There are 5 violations of employee discipline towards working time efficiency in the general and equipment section, provided that 3 people are given light sanctions, and 2 people are given moderate sanctions. After a more accurate analysis was carried out, it turned out that several factors caused the violation, namely the lack of (1) communication, (2) resources, (3) disposition (attitude of the executor), and (4) bureaucratic structure. Communication between colleagues, both superiors and subordinates, is minimal, resulting in minimal human resources and work discipline knowledge in general and equipment. Besides, implementers or stakeholders' attitude towards the disposition of socialization activities regarding the implementation of work discipline for Civil Servants is not followed up.

Keywords---civil servants, discipline implementation, discipline knowledge, government regulation, socialization activities.

Introduction

In carrying out government tasks and national development, it depends on the State apparatus's ability, especially the State Civil Apparatus. Therefore, to achieve the national development goals, namely realizing a civil society that is law-abiding, modern civilized, democratic, prosperous, just, and with high morals, it is necessary to have employees

who serve as public servants of the State based on loyalty and obedience to Pancasila and the Constitution 1945. (Wasistiono, 2002; Wance & Djae, 2019; Kaliky et al., 2020; Wance et al., 2020).

The code of conduct for State Civil Servants as public servants is what is called Government Regulation Number 30 of 1980 in the obligation of the State Civil Apparatus that the State Civil Apparatus is a Government apparatus that behaves well and becomes a role model for the community (Beerepoot & Beerepoot, 2007; Shaffer, 1995; Graafland & Smid, 2017). The awareness of the State Civil Apparatus behavior towards the duties and obligations or the work that is their responsibility has a very positive impact on the organization. The task or work itself will be a source of seriousness and discipline in carrying out tasks so that the results can meet the standards that have been established both in the embodiment of implementation standards and operational standards. Thus, discipline is a starting point for all successes to achieve the goals of an organization. The application of discipline in an organization is intended so that all employees in the agency are willing to obey and obey any applicable rules without coercion voluntarily. Good work discipline can be seen from the high awareness of employees in obeying and obeying all applicable rules and regulations, a great sense of responsibility for their respective duties, and increasing their employees' efficiency and performance. From the results of observations made by the author at the General Affairs and Equipment Section of the West Halmahera Regency, that in its implementation there are still various problems related to the discipline of the State Civil Apparatus as contained in Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 concerning the Discipline of the State Civil Apparatus.

First, the discipline of State Civil Apparatus is following Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 concerning Discipline of State Civil Apparatus in the General Section and Equipment of the Regional Secretariat of West Halmahera Regency not maximally according to the rules, because in Article 3 Number 1 and 2 that every State Civil Apparatus is obliged to take an oath State Civil Apparatus to pledge; take the oath/promise of office. However, the real condition of State Civil Apparatus performance is not following the oaths that have been pronounced. The performance of State Civil Apparatus has not been satisfactory to the community's wishes.

Second, State Civil Apparatus in the General Affairs and Equipment Section of the West Halmahera District Secretariat has not fully carried out actions following its obligations as State Civil Apparatus. This is seen from going out and going to work that is not by the stipulated time, should have entered the office at 08.00 WIT and go home 16.00 WIT. Even though this obligation is contained in Article 3 Number 11, it is explained that coming to work and obeying the provisions of working hours the electronic absence (finger) of employees does not meet the predetermined time, and there are still employees who often arrive late and come home from work not yet.

Third, State Civil Apparatus disciplinary actions have not been maximally carried out, even though Article 5 and Article 6 explain that State Civil Apparatus who do not comply with the provisions as referred to in Article 3 and/or Article 4 will be subject to disciplinary action; By not overriding the provisions in criminal laws and regulations, State Civil Apparatus who commit disciplinary offenses will be subject to disciplinary action.

Concept of the state civil apparatus

The regional state civil apparatus is the provincial/regency/city-state civil apparatus, whose salaries are borne by the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget and work for the regional government or are employed outside its parent agency. (Nurcholish, 2005). State Civil Apparatus employees are employees mandated by Law Number 05 of 2014 concerning the State Civil Apparatus. Apart from being the implementer of a public policy and service, State Civil Apparatus employees must also act as the glue and unifier of the nation. State Civil Apparatus employees are in charge of:

- 1) Implement public policies made by Civil Service Officers by the provisions of laws and regulations;
- 2) Providing professional and quality public services; and
- 3) Strengthen the unity and integrity of the Republic of Indonesia. State Civil Apparatus employees should implement existing public policies following the duties of assigned officials. However, the professional and quality of work must be owned by State Civil Apparatus employees.

Regional employees are state civil servants. The state civil apparatus's position as an element of the state apparatus is tasked with providing services to the community in a professional, honest, fair, and equitable manner in carrying out state, government, and development tasks. In their position and duties, civil servants must be neutral from all political groups and parties' influence and not be discriminatory in providing services to the community. For civil servants to maintain this principle of neutrality, civil servants are prohibited from becoming members and/or administrators of political parties.

Policy implementation theory

According to Wayne Parsons, implementation is change, how change occurs, and how the possibility of change can be raised; it is also a study of political life's microstructure, how organizations outside and inside the political system conduct their affairs and interact with one another. What are their motivations for acting in this way, and what other motivations might make them act differently? (Parsons, 2006; Aslan, 2019).

According to Widjaja (2003), various implementation issues that arise must be of concern and need to be analyzed and anticipated so that the implementation of village autonomy can run well, so that good, efficient, and effective governance patterns are created to provide services to the public, in carrying out a policy must be accompanied by the responsibility to the public so that it meets the expectations of the community, the oversight function carried out by the legislature and the public needs to be carried out so that transparency in managing existing resources. According to Mazmanian & Sabatier (1983) policy implementation is implementing basic policy decisions, usually in the form of laws. Still, it can also take the form of important executive orders or decisions or judicial decisions. Preparing implementation, which is to think and calculate the various possibilities of success and failure, including obstacles or opportunities, exist, and organizational skills to implement the program (Bakry, 2010; Dachi, 2017). Based on the above opinion, it appears that policy implementation is not only limited to the actions or behavior of alternative bodies or bureaucratic units that are responsible for implementing programs and causing compliance with target groups but more than that, it also continues with a network of influential political, socio-economic forces on the behavior of all parties involved, and in the end, some impacts are expected, and that is not expected.

According to Lubis (2007), successful implementation is relatively easy if the policies are distributive, the regulatory policies are modern, and the distributive policies are low; various policy areas have different relationship patterns, which means that in the redistributive area, there is more bargaining bidding and politics rather than in the distributive area, where there may be greater control pressure. Such a public service accountability model that is responsive to the local community's demands can be expected to be able to solve practical problems governing procedures, setting costs, time and complaint mechanisms, and determining service facilities (Herizal et al., 2020).

Concept of public policy

POLICY is interpreted as an action that leads to the goal proposed by a person, group, or government in a particular environment concerning their particular constraints while seeking opportunities to achieve a goal or realize a desired target (Hasibuan, 2003). James Anderson stated policy is an action that has a purpose carried out by an actor or some actors to solve a problem (Nurcholish, 2005). According to Ibrahim & Tjahja (2019), that public policy is carried out through a planning process that has been analysed comprehensively POLICY public as a permanent decision is characterized by consistency and repeatability of the behaviour of those who create and those who abide by the decision (Agustino, 2008). Public policies are policies made by state administrators, in this case, the government. Usually stipulated in the form of statutory regulations (Subarsono, 2005). Public policy is a long series of more or less interconnected options made by government or state agencies or offices, formulated in specific issue areas: such as defense, energy, health, education, welfare, and crime (Dunn, 2015).

Research Methods

This research uses qualitative research by focusing on the implementation of Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 concerning Civil Servant Discipline in the General Affairs and Equipment Section of the Regional Secretariat of West Halmahera Regency. This qualitative research emphasizes inductive analysis, not deductive analysis. The data collected is not intended to support or reject the hypotheses that have been compiled before the research begins. Still, the abstracts are arranged as specificities collected and grouped through a data collection process that has been carried out carefully (Prasetyo & Sutopo, 2018; Berg, 2001; Creswell, 2009). The data collected are in the form of words and pictures. Moreover, everything that is gathered is likely to be the key to what has been researched. Thus, the research report contains data quotations to provide an overview of the report's presentation (Meleong, 2008).

Results and Discussion

Implementation of Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 Concerning the Discipline of Civil Servants

Every regulation that will be implemented needs one stage, namely socialization. Activity social sanction inseparable part of the implementation of the policy. This is because socialization is the process of activities to provide information and explain the meaning of the policy. The stage of policy socialization has a significant meaning in implementing regulations. Therefore, the socialization that is carried out is limited to once or twice but needs to be carried out continuously every time so that it is easily understood and understood by the general public.

The context of Government Regulation 53/2010 in the environment

The General Affairs and Equipment Section of the West Halmahera District Secretariat has been socialized to all employees who work in the General and Equipment Section. The following interview with Safri Dengo as the Head of General Affairs & Equipment for the Regional Secretariat of West Halmahera Regency said that:

This government regulation is excellent, with the government regulations number 53 of 2010, because it can improve Employee Work Discipline with the government regulations number. 53 of 2010. Employees know the regulations referred to, either through a circular or a meeting with government regulations Regional Work Units leaders. For government regulations socialization activities, the leadership conducts it in various ways, including morning apples and routine meetings to circulars delivered to employees. Meanwhile, the socialization of work time discipline is always carried out at morning roll call and home from work, the leadership, always reminds the time to come to the office to work and go home. (Interview on March 4, 2019).

Based on the interview results, Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 has been well socialized to employees in the General Affairs and Equipment Section of the West Halmahera District Secretariat. The leadership's socialization activities are carried out in various ways, starting from morning apples and apples home every time the socialization is carried out, routine meetings to delivery through circular letters distributed to civil servants. Syamsir Ali also conveyed another expression as the Head of Sub Division of Administration & Personnel, said that:

Regulation of Government Regulation number 53 of 2010 concerning Civil Servant Discipline clearly and firmly regulates the discipline of Civil Servants. However, there is a need for continuous outreach to employees. The socialization activities for PP 53/2010 were carried out in various ways, starting from every morning/evening apple that was delivered and even during a meeting between the leaders of the Regional Work Units. Confirmation of socialization is carried out by the leadership to be passed on to employees in the respective work units. Furthermore, work time is also socialized, especially coming and going home, must be following the provisions. (Interview dated March 6, 2019).

The socialization of Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 has been carried out in various ways, with the hope that civil servants in the General Affairs and Equipment Section of the West Halmahera District Secretariat can improve work time discipline, both discipline when coming and going home and being able to generate morale for civil servants. Several important points were made in the socialization of government regulations number 53/2010 concerning Civil Servant Discipline, namely:

Table 1
Socialization of government regulations number 53/2010 concerning Civil Servant Discipline

Light	Moderate	Weight
a. Verbal warning;	a. Postponement of periodic salary increases for one year;	a. Demotion to a lower level for three years;
b. Written warning; and	b. Postponement of promotion for one year; and	b. Transfer in the context of a lower level demotion;
c. Dissatisfied statement in writing.	c. Demotion with one level lower for one year	c. Release from office;
		d. Honorably dismissed not at his request as State Civil Apparatus; and
		e. Dishonorable discharge as State Civil Apparatus

To realize the enforcement of State Civil Apparatus discipline in general, especially State Civil Apparatus in the General Affairs and Equipment Section of West Halmahera Regency. Implementing State Civil Apparatus discipline enforcement in the General and Equipment Division environment is critical to realize and support the acceleration of bureaucratic reform for improving government performance. State Civil Apparatus' ability to comply with obligations and avoid prohibitions stipulated in the statutory regulations and official regulations subject to disciplinary action if not obeyed or violated.

Enforcement of Government Regulation Number 53/2010

The presence of Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 has several objectives, namely First, the purpose of Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 concerning Civil Servant Discipline is that Civil Servants in the General Affairs and Equipment Section of the West Halmahera District Secretariat are disciplined, and this has become the basis for employees Civilians to work following the main duties and functions of each position held by employees.

Second, the standard of success of Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 concerning Civil Servant Discipline is that all employees must be aware that employees must be responsible for discipline, especially discipline in working time.

The two objectives mentioned above clearly state that civil servants' discipline is essential to be implemented. However, in the application of discipline, it must also be supported by prosecution or enforcement for undisciplined civil servants. Employees feel responsible for always obeying Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010. Following is an interview with Safri Dengo as Head of General Affairs & The equipment of the West Halmahera Regency Regional Secretariat stated that:

If the disciplinary enforcement of civil servants has been carried out, some state civil servants have also been subject to sanctions. So, there are employees who are not disciplined in working time according to the provisions (for example; their attendance is not following the rules, often skips work, does not go to the office without the knowledge of the leadership), then the rules must be enforced without favoritism, and if they are guilty they must be given punishment, this is a form from disciplinary enforcement in terms of working time. (Interview on March 4, 2019).

Types of Sanctions / Punishment for State Civil Apparatus

Discipline is essential to use as a direction to form and train someone to do something to be good and is a process to foster a person's feelings in maintaining and improving organizational goals objectively through compliance with implementing organizational rules. Implementing discipline is, of course, the responsibility of all parties for employees, both personally and institutionally. However, sometimes employees are always undisciplined or violate disciplinary rules in an agency. State Civil Servants as government officials and public servants are always ready to carry out the tasks that have become their responsibility properly (Hao et al., 2015; Ishida & Matsushima, 2009; Dalal & Chahal, 2016). Still, often in a government agency, their employees commit disciplinary violations such as arriving late, leaving prematurely, working while chatting, and deviating other irregularities that lead to ineffective employees concerned.

Employee disciplinary actions often occur in an agency, ranging from mild undisciplined conditions to more severe levels. Thus, there is an approach that uses an organizational route in the form of strategy formulation the role of a leader, and there is also a personal approach. But whatever the degree, these disciplinary employees need to be dealt with as early as possible to minimize the level of discipline that is even worse. Disciplinary violation is any words, writings, or actions of the State Civil Apparatus who do not comply with their obligations and/or violate the prohibitions on State Civil Apparatus disciplinary provisions, both inside and outside working hours. A disciplinary penalty is a punishment imposed on the State Civil Service for violating State Civil Apparatus disciplinary regulations. Based on these rules, civil servants who violate discipline rules on working time are directly subject to sanctions/penalties under the State Civil Apparatus discipline provisions.

The absence of State Civil Servants in the General Affairs and Equipment Section of the West Halmahera District Secretariat is due to causes so that State Civil Apparatus is not disciplined at work when entering the office and even returning from work. The statement as explained by Donsonas the Head of Subdivision of Protocol and Equipment Section stated that:

In the General & Equipment Section, some State Civil Apparatus are sometimes not disciplined in working time, arriving late and returning home is also not by the regulations. Not disciplined working time is because the leadership also does not always supervise State Civil Apparatus discipline; there is a warning from the new

supervisor who is carried out by the supervisor. Whereas State Civil Apparatus disciplinary supervision is very necessary to know the discipline of State Civil Apparatus at work, if there are State Civil Apparatus who are negligent and undisciplined, they can be given sanctions or penalties according to the applicable provisions in government regulations Number 53 of 2010. (Interview on March 13, 2019).

Discipline is essential to use as a direction to form and train someone to do something to be good and is a process to foster a person's feelings in maintaining and improving organizational goals objectively through compliance with implementing organizational rules. Implementing discipline is, of course, the responsibility of all parties for employees, both personally and institutionally. However, sometimes employees are always undisciplined or violate disciplinary rules in an agency. State Civil Servants as government officials and public servants are always ready to carry out the tasks that have become their responsibility properly. Still, often in a government agency, their employees commit disciplinary violations such as arriving late, leaving prematurely, working while chatting, and deviating other irregularities that lead to ineffective employees concerned.

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Based on the interview results, it was explained that the State Civil Apparatus in the General Affairs and Equipment Section of the Regional Secretariat of West Halmahera Regency often violates work time discipline. Work time discipline violations vary widely, starting from late entry to the office and going home not following the provisions; of course, this violation committed by State Civil Apparatus greatly affects the performance in the General and Equipment Section so that the work is more and more pile up and the completion of working time also really takes time which is quite a long time.

Violation of working time discipline should be given a sanction or punishment according to the type of violation committed. The General and Equipment Section has given sanctions/penalties to State Civil Apparatus who are not disciplined for a working time as many as five people, giving various sanctions, there are mild and moderate punishments.

Table 2
Applicable Employee Names Discipline Punishment

Applicable Employee Names Discipline Punishment	Punishment Type		
	Light	Medium	Weight
R	√		
IF		√	
M		√	
SP	√		
GM	√		

Source: General Affairs and Equipment Section of the Regional Secretariat of the District. West Halmahera, 2019

Safri Dengo conveyed the same statement as the Head of General Affairs & Equipment for the Regional Secretariat of West Halmahera Regency, said that:

State Civil Apparatus that are not disciplined in working time do exist and have been carefully controlled and then given sanctions or penalties following government regulations 53/2010. Disciplinary violations of working time are indeed very influential in terms of employee work. More and more work is done. It also takes a long time and not to mention that there is new work every day. Many factors cause State Civil Apparatus in the General and Equipment Section environment to be lazy or not disciplined in working time, ranging from the ethics/morals of State Civil Apparatus who view discipline as not important so that the work given is not ready to be done; there are also thoughts of too low salary or welfare, and supervision that has not been carried out yet, so it is necessary to carry out continuous supervision every day. (Interview on 04 March 2019).

Based on the interview results and the list of the table above, it shows that enforcing work time discipline is the obligation of superiors or authorized officials, in this case, the leadership/superiors. Superiors or officials who are authorized to enforce work time discipline must be firm regardless of who they are. With such an attitude, they can show themselves as true leaders. The disciplinary penalties given are none other than to improve and educate the State Civil Apparatus itself and launch activities in carrying out official duties properly to provide excellent service to the community. In Government Regulation Number 53 of 2010 concerning State Civil Apparatus Discipline, it explains that the causes of disciplinary violations of the State Civil Apparatus include the following:

- 1) Unfair treatment from a leader to subordinates can cause subordinates to commit disciplinary violations. Because they feel they are treated differently and feel neglected and not taken included in certain activities. As a result, subordinates are lazy to enter the office, lazy to work, and rarely in the workplace;
- 2) Lack of employee welfare can also encourage the State Civil Apparatus to be undisciplined. Increasing the costs of necessities, expensive education costs, and prices of necessities always go up so that the salary received is insufficient to meet daily needs. As a result, State Civil Apparatus is subject to objections, corruption, and part-time work during working hours;
- 3) Unhealthy career patterns, leaders who ignore subordinates' careers, work experience, loyalty, dedication, not being promoted for a long time, monotonous work, and unclear task patterns make State Civil Apparatus feel bored and neglect work;
- 4) Bad management, in one office, good management and administration should be applied. On the other hand, if the management is bad, there is no control over employees, there is no clear division of tasks, lack of facilities, weak human resources can cause State Civil Apparatus to work according to their own will and capability;
- 5) Weak was at supervision in an institution carried out by the leader to subordinates is very weak so that subordinates feel unsupervised, are free to do activities and subordinates think office work is not important; consequently, subordinates do not work seriously, subordinates do not make work results and reports made out of accordance with reality;
- 6) Violations are not dealt with firmly. The leadership does not understand the disciplinary rules, feels sorry for them, and is not afraid of disciplinary action, and is not afraid to commit disciplinary actions;
- 7) The exemplary crisis is that superiors are not disciplined, superiors do not understand disciplinary rules, and superiors give irregular circumstances. As a result, supervisors and subordinates are neither disciplined;
- 8) Lack of motivation: the leadership pays attention to subordinates and does not stimulate the creation of work passion. State Civil Apparatus does not have the enthusiasm to improve work performance and shows an innovative and responsive desire for their duties;
- 9) The State Civil Apparatus disciplinary regulations are not understood, the factor of understanding the rules also causes employees to violate the rules so they are not disciplined.

Conclusion

Discipline Violations of civil servants in the General and Equipment Section are very diverse so that the imposition of sanctions is also adjusted to the violations committed. The number of civil servants who violate the discipline of working time is five people, provided that three people are given light sanctions and two people are given moderate sanctions. The implementation of government regulations number 53 of 2010 concerning Civil Servant Discipline in the General and Equipment Section has been running quite well. This is evidenced by the implementation of socialization activities for State Civil Apparatus in the General and Equipment Section, while the enforcement of

State Civil Apparatus discipline has been carried out without regard to favoritism. State Civil Apparatus violates the work time discipline, they will be immediately given sanctions according to the level of violation. Four factors are affecting the implementation of government regulations number 53 of 2010 concerning State Civil Apparatus Discipline, namely (1) communication, (2) resources, (3) disposition and (4) bureaucratic structure.

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